

The Trajectory of Transformative Research as an Inclusive Qualitative Research Approach to Social Issues

Bunmi Isaiah Omodan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 05, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: October 07, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Qualitative research, Methodology, Transformative paradigm, Participatory Action Research, Social issues.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4071952</p>	<p><i>Experiences in research exploration have revealed how best to respond to social issues in education research, most especially that bothers on social relationships and differences, among others. The literature also reiterated the place of positivism/post-positivism paradigm (quantitative approach) in interrogating these social issues. In this article, I contended that such approach is too subjective, undemocratic and overbearing. I argue that the best and most productive form of research design that could adequately respond to the social problems is the Participatory Action Research (PAR), lensed through Transformative Paradigm (TP). This is because the thrust of PAR and TP are essential to transform people and their predicaments by making them co-researchers where they are able to share and construct knowledge as a solution to their problems. This was argued with an exposition of philosophical assumptions underpinning the choice TP from it axiological, ontological, epistemological and methodological stance. The study, therefore, formulates Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) as a new technique of data analysis which enables social issue researchers to rationalise the sociality of the people living with the problem. This is appropriate for interpreting data in transformational research.</i></p>

1. Introduction

There has been numerous interdisciplinary researches conducted across the field of social sciences in a bid to respond to so many social issues, ranging from conflict and crisis management issues, social instabilities and unrests, social and political emancipation, and general emancipatory research (Akinnubi&Kayode. 2012; Eric &Urho, 2015; Akinyeye, 2019; Akparep, 2019). These researches have come up with one or more research findings and solutions to the issues. However, the aforementioned researches are not the bone of contention, but some of those social researchers that used *Positivism/Postpositivism paradigm* (quantitative approaches) solely to respond to the issues might have jettison some quality research inputs, processes, and outputs. That is, many of such social issue research seems not to have reflected the mind, the reality and the situation of their research focus. This is because it appears unfair when human being and its sociality is subjected to one reality generated from statistical interpretation. This according to the argument of pragmatists, interpretivist, and transformative practitioners, is unfair because the reality in social issues are more than one as against the claim of positivist and post-positivist researchers (Kivunja&Kuyini, 2017; Dean, 2018; Dube, &Hlalele, 2018; Kaushik& Walsh, 2019).

In the beliefs of Quantitative (Positivist/Postpositivist) researcher, the reality is one and the same, that is, they believe that an answer to a problem must be subjected to statistical interpretation and whatever the output of such process is, becomes a solution. This is too subjective because its reality has jettisoned the supposed logical objectivism (Aliyu, Bello, Kasim& Martin, 2014) and at times, is based on perception (Waismann, 2011). In such case, they might have forgotten that the tools were created to process whatever is inputted into it, therefore, may misinterpret the minds of the researched and thereby subject the minds of the participants into an ordinary object (statistical tool).

The intention of this study is, therefore, not to condemn the validity or originality of quantitative researchers and their researches, but to contend that, when it comes to social issues, where the researcher intend to understand, interpret and or make sense of the social problem, the people/researched must be involved. Not only to be involved but to have an equal participatory pedestal for them to be able to contribute to the planning, process and the output of the research. This, according to Mahali and Swartz (2018) enables the researcher(s) to be able to understand the people and their problem. Such research process is not only fair but democratic and emancipative (Aasgaard, Borg, Karlsson, 2012). When there is an involvement of the researched/participants, in the process and the solution generation stage, gives the researched a sense of belonging and not as an ordinary

object but as an important subject needed for community emancipation and development. Therefore, to expose the expediency of transformative research as an inclusive qualitative research approach to social issues, the below-piloting question was answered.

Research Question

1. How can the nitty-gritty of transformative research process be exposed as the best research process to uncover social problems in research?

Research Objectives

The above question looks robust and general, therefore, needed to be piloted by the following research objectives;

1. The study examined the conceptualisation of transformative research process and its relevance to solving social issues in research.
2. The study also explored the qualitative research methods that are best to implement the transformative research process when dealing with social issues.

In order to achieve the above objectives, a coherent presentation of argument was made by rationalising concepts based on their hierarchy of importance. That is, the way and manner they should be considered when implemented in social researches. I start by explaining research methodology, paradigms and the choice of Transformative Paradigm (TP). Participatory Action Research (PAR) as a research design that best implement the principles of TP in transformative research was rationalized in line with its democratic tendency in the group of participants who share the same sociality. In the same process, the study presented Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) as a new method of analysing data in social research. This study forms a part of a large research project approved by the ethical committee of the University of the Free State with approval number UFS-HSD2018/1105.

Describing Research Methodology

Methodology in research has been conceptualised as a way of studying how research is done. That is, how to solve a particular research problem (Kothari, 2004). This is to say that research methodology could mean the steps adopted by the researcher to expose and inquire into a problem alongside the logic behind it. The above concept is not totally different from the view of Scotland (2012), who sees research methodology as a theoretical process of inquiry which involves the analysis of procedures, principles and assumptions in a specific approach to enquiry. According to Chilisa and Kawulich (2012), the thought to choose a research methodology starts with the decision in which the research paradigm is informing the study. This, according to them will guide the researcher on the philosophical beliefs about the nature of values, knowledge, and reality. Moreover, the theoretical framework informing the choice of literature, interpretation and the research practices are also included. According to them, the building up of research methodology begins with a stance on the following questions: What paradigm informs the study? What theories inform the choice of the research topic? What research approach is appropriate? What types and sources of data might you be able to use to help answer your research questions? How does theory inform your approach to data analysis and interpretation? By what and whose standards are the design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of research findings deemed valid and reliable? In a bid to answering these questions, one needs to first identify which paradigm is best for social research based on the intention of the researcher. In other words, the position of research paradigm is very fundamental in planning a research.

Conceptualising Research Paradigm

Literature from the notable scholars in the field of research paradigm has been able to give explicit understanding to the concept of the word “paradigm”. The word was first used by Thomas Kuhn in his work “the Structure of Scientific Revolution” in 1962 to mean a philosophical way of thinking (Kuhn, 1962; Kivunja&Kuyini, 2017). The word in its Greek etymology means pattern (Kivunja&Kuyini, 2017). That is, a paradigm is a basic pattern or worldview guiding the researcher. This is made up of the theoretical assumptions and laws and techniques appropriate for the scientific community (Chalmers, 1982; Guba& Lincoln, 1994). In the world of research, it is described as the researcher’s worldview, perspective, thinking, belief and schools of thought that guide the interpretation, meaning and sense of a research data (Lather, 1986; Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006). From these definitions, one could derive that paradigm is the surrounding belief and how researchers perceive the world, live the world and act in the world of research. Therefore, a paradigm is a way of understanding the reality of the world and studying it (Rehman&Alharthi, 2010).

By describing the worldview of paradigm, the nature of reality known as ontology, the ethics and value known as axiology, the ways of knowing known as epistemology and the approaches to inquiry known as a methodology cannot be underestimated (Patton, 2002; Rehman& Khalid Alharthi, 2010; Chilisa&Kawulich,

2012). Ontology as one of the elements, according to Scotland (2012) is concerned with the assumption into the world of reality. This could post a question such as what do we believe about the nature of reality. Axiology, on the other hand, is about the ethical issues needed to be considered when planning a research proposal, that is, the philosophical approach to making decisions of value or the right decisions (Kivunja&Kuyini, 2017; Finnis, 1980). Another element is Epistemology. According to Chilisa and Kawulich (2012), it inquires into the nature of knowledge and truth. That is its inquiries into the sources of knowledge, the reliability of the sources, the nature of the knowledge and the characteristics of the knowledge itself. Lastly, a methodology is referred to as the theoretically informed approach used in the production of data (Rehman&Alharthi, 2010). This, according to Shah and Al-Bargi (2013:253) involves a well-articulated and carefully selected research design, methods, and approaches to investigation. Apart from these elements, the world of paradigm is divided into various divisions based on researchers' worldviews. These divides are tagged positivism, post-positivism, constructivism, transformative, and postcolonial indigenous paradigms (Chilisa&Kawulich, 2012).

These paradigms have their own peculiarities. Positivism is on the belief that there is only one way to knowledge construction. That is, the school of thought believes that the paradigm is peculiar to natural science research procedures (Dammak, 2019). Though, a lot of social scientists also use it. Hence, they are committed to scientific neutrality, statistical measurement, and quantifiable elements in knowledge development (Seale, 2000). Post-positivism, on the other hand, was of the opinion that no matter how faithfully the scientist adheres to scientific methods of research, research outcomes are neither totally objective nor unquestionably certain (Crotty, 1998). Hence, this deviation proposed more of objectivity to the research process, which makes it a less strict form of positivism (Chilisa&Kawulich, 2012). Constructivist/Interpretivist is viewed by Creswell (2013:36) as an objective process in the quest for reality. That is, there are multiple realities. This school of thought believes that people are creative and actively construct their social reality based on experience (Dammak, 2019). Transformative school of thought argued that Positivist/PostPositivist, Constructivist/Interpretivist are the agents of marginalisation (Fixico, 1998; Mihesuah, 2005). Therefore, there is a need to form a common theme of emancipating and transforming communities through group action (Mertens, 2010). Lastly, Postcolonial Indigenous is the fourth paradigm which is targeted towards disempowered or historically oppressed social groups (Chilisa, 2011; Sakyi, 2017).

In this study, attention is placed on Transformative school of thought, because its major assumption is to emancipate and transform the researched, the communities and the concerned through group activities and with a democratically informed research process. This is because, all social problem as argued above, is either needed to be understood, interested or emancipated for the purpose of an active change in the lives of the community people (the researched).

Transformative paradigm as a Research Lens for research in social Issues

Transformative paradigm is appropriate for studies that are based on social and emancipatory philosophy, approach and research design. The research philosophy here borders on any underpinning theories that fall within the theoretical prescription of transformative, such as critical theory, postcolonial discourses, feminist theories, race-specific and neo-Marxist theories (Chilisa&Kawulich, 2012:7). On the methodical design of such study, transformative paradigm according to Mertens, (2005) and Dube (2016) also falls within the purview of participatory action researchers, with a focus on the dynamics of emancipation. The choice for transformative is not limited to the philosophy and its research method alone, but the method of data generation for such study, could be an interview, social observation, interactions and above all, focus group discussion (Romm, 2015:413) fall within the ambit of transformative paradigm. However, the elements of TP, such as axiology, ontology, epistemology and methodology are explained below.

Axiology of Transformative Paradigm

Axiology is a philosophical branch or an assumption of paradigm which addresses issues of ethics to be considered when planning research (Finnis, 2080). It also promotes moral, cultural respect, social justice and human rights. It equally addresses inequities and reciprocity (Mertens, 2010; Mertens, 2017). This is to say that the axiology of transformative paradigm defines and respects what is right and what is wrong in the conduct of research. According to Kivunja and Kuyini (2017), it borders on what particular values needed for every process of research, including participants' treatment, the data and the targeted audience of the research. This analysis could be said to have answered the question of ethical behaviour in the research process. That is, the regards for values of research participants must be considered. Hence, the axiological assumption frowns at the indiscriminate treatment of humanity in the community of participants. By so doing, it lays fundamental emphasis on ethical responsibilities of researchers to understand and respect humanity and its diversities in order to challenge societal coloniality and/or inequality that perpetuates oppressive ways of doing (Mertens&

Wilson 2012). Thus, the assumption of axiology in transformative paradigm is on the fundamentality of the participants' values that must be respected with almost recognition to humanity and diversity for the purpose of emancipation.

Ontology of Transformative Paradigm

Ontology from general perspectives is referred to as the view of reality and being, which will likely lead to the choice of theoretical framework in research (Mack, 2010). According to Grix (2004), ontology is an assumption made about the nature of social reality, such as; what exists, how and why. The ontology of the transformative paradigm is built from historical realism, where there is a belief that reality exists outside the mind (Elshafe, 2013). The reality, according to this ontological assumption, is shaped historically, socially, culturally, and ethnically (Guba& Lincoln, 1982). Since the reality is constructed based on sociality, the researcher needs to critically examine the issue of sociality, power and politics in the quest for reality (Mertens, 2007; Lather, 2006). This is to say that the experiences of the community of researchers and/or the participants are fundamental in the transformational process of inquiring a particular phenomenon reality that is visible, and the other is deep. From the above conceptualisation, it is logical to say that reality is multidimensional. This, according to Chilisa and Kawulich (2012) is divided into a surface structures that are unobservable. According to Chilisa (2011), the historical orientation and the theoretical framing help to unmask the deep structure. From the above, it is expedient to note that reality that shaped the social issues is politically inclined, sociality embedded, historically and culturally traceable and socially unpleasant.

Epistemology of Transformative Paradigm

The assumptions of epistemology bother on the relationships between researchers and participants (Mertens, 2007). This relationship is established to understand the culture and to build trust between the researchers and participants (Mertens, 2010). In the transformative paradigm, the issue of relationship and trust in the process of knowledge generation is essential because it seeks to understand versions of reality and power issues. This is why the establishment of interactive relationship is needed to be able to understand and deal with power differentials within community members (Mertens, 2012). This makes the knowledge generation to be transactional and objective (Guba& Lincoln, 2005). Therefore, this assumption is on the quest for what is the truth and maintains that knowledge is true, which must be turned into actual practice in order to transform and/or empower people. Hence, the first step towards transformation is to ensure that knowledge is unanimously constructed between the researchers and the participants towards transformation (Chan, 2005). That is, a piece of true knowledge cannot be discovered when the research process is merely subjected to a structured questionnaire as claimed by the quantitative researchers. I, therefore, argue that the knowledge needed to transform the people is expected to be constructed alongside the concerned stakeholders.

Methodology of Transformative Paradigm

In the methodological assumption of transformative paradigm, the purpose of research is to destroy the myth, illusions, and false knowledge and empower people to act and to transform their own society indigenously (Chilisa&Kawulich, 2012). This assumption was a deviation from positivist ways of doing research in order to promote participants' recognition in the process of addressing human and social issues. This, according to Moleko (2018), makes the researchers and the researched assume the position of being recognised as co-researchers. This enables them to work together and address the issue at stake without power supremacy (Mahlomaholo&Netshandama, 2010). The common designs in the methodological assumption of this paradigm are usually participatory rural appraisal approach and action research (Mahlomaholo&Netshandama, 2010; Dube, 2016; Moleko, 2018).

In such approach to research, the participants are involved in the process of identification and definition of a problem, data generation and analysis, recommendation of findings and also engaged in the practices of the findings (MacDonald, 201; Kemmis, 2010). Based on the above, the stance of methodological assumptions of transformative paradigm could be smoothly implemented with some research design, such as participatory action research, among others. I focused on the Participatory Action Research (PAR) because it empowers people by involving them in the planning, implementation and in communicating the research findings. This ensure a democratic and robust research productivity (Mertens, 2009).

Evolution of Participatory Action Research

Participatory action research is traceably emanated from Kurt Lewin, a Prussian psychologist and Jewish refugee from Nazi Germany who conducted a form of transformative research targeted at social problems such as segregation, discrimination, dehumanisation and assimilation immediately after the world war II (Reason &

Bradbury, 2008; MacDonald, 2012). Lewin's research predominantly centred toward change and the study of the impact of the change. The intention was to find solutions to a particular social menace with an informed change (MacDonald, 2012). In the same vein, Kemmis and McTaggart (2005) also traced the evolution of PAR to Lewin who brought about the nomenclature renowned as "action research" which spread to multidimensional disciplines. The second generation of action research conducted by John Elliot and Clem Adelman brought about developmental advancement to the development of PAR, while the third generation of PAR advocated for more critical emancipatory approaches (Morales, 2016). The fourth-generation further demanded a more articulate and actionist approach where the researchers are expected to connect their research process to inclusivity in the form of a social movement (Kemmis&McTaggart, 2005; Morales, 2016). Having understood the brief historical background of PAR, there is need to conceptualised PAR and its objectives in social research.

Conceptualising Participatory Action Research

PAR, according to Eruera (2010) is a qualitative research process associated with social science which developed as a positive deviation from traditional and positivist perspective in an attempt to address social and human interplays. PAR is traced to radical tradition towards participation, action and development of knowledge to respond to social injustices, inclusivity and above all, it empowers and emancipates the marginalised (Seymour-Rolls & Hughes, 2000; Khan & Chovanec, 2010). That is, it requires active participation between the researchers and the researched who are enlightened to identify, analyse and address issues of concern. This definition shows that PAR is a bundle of activities that encompass investigation (research), educationally work and act towards change (Brown & Tandon, 1983). The implication is that researcher working under this design conduct the research in conjunction with the participants (researched). They jointly identify social problems, decide the process together, plan the research process together, implement and generate new knowledge simultaneously. PAR combines research education with practical development of interventions where the voices of the marginalised could be heard and respected (Kemmis, 2010). Perhaps, this is confirmed by Tshelane (2013) that PAR values indigenous and local knowledge of the marginalised groups as a basis for revolutionary actions, which can improve the lives of people.

PAR as a participatory way of conducting research, appears to be democratic in nature considering its characteristics that pay important attention to the equality and power differences between and/or among the researched community. These democratic tendencies according to Zuber-Skerritt (2015) and Wood and McAteer (2017) encourage full involvement of the community in the process of creating knowledge to sustain empowerment of the less privileged and undervalued people of the community. Hence, I, therefore, argue that trusting the unanimous partnership between the researchers and the researched (the community) to concrete knowledge and action is democracy. From the foregoing, the Participatory Action Research (PAR) could be said to be a process of generating and rationalising knowledge for social change. This process involves the people with the concerns experienced, who are probably living with the problem and experiencing the problem under research.

Objectives of Participatory Action Research (PAR)

PAR, as a research design, has targets, among which is why various researchers all over the world consider it very quintessential in dealing with social and human issues. Dube (2016) analytically itemised various aims and objectives which are: PAR prioritised working with the marginalised communities, helps to contest power differentials in research and research process. It also helps to transform theories into practice with collaborative spirits, and above all, it engenders values of indigenous knowledge. The implication of these is that it aims to transform both theories and practice that could transform society to be a better place with harmonious relationships (Kemmis&McTaggart, 2007; Tsotetsi, 2013; Dube, 2016). Coherently, PAR in its focus also constructs local knowledge to the advantage of the marginalised in the community because it empowers and encourages ordinary people in the community to construct knowledge (Francis, 2012), which according to Dube (2016) contributes to the democratisation of research process. This may be because it inquires and utilises the community assets to the process of constructing knowledge and taking of action for a definite change (Leowenson, Laurell, Hogstedt, D'Ambruoso& Shroff, 2014).

Qhosola (2016)'s argument also believes that PAR empowers the oppressed individuals to partake in the process that brings social change, which also benefits them to build capacity development through participation. This, according to her, is achieved by bringing different stakeholders with different expertise together to help mold the participants and the entire community. This further confirms the argument of Cameron and Gibson (2005) that knowledge gained in the process of participation is applied to shape the lives of ordinary people. In the view of Tsotetsi (2013), having said this, I argued that PAR addresses issues of inclusion, social justice and empowerment of the oppressed minority in marginalised communities. That is, it is practically against the

systematic production and reproduction of inequalities among community dwellers. However, the objectives of PAR as exemplified above are an eye-opener to achieving the objectives of social issues in research.

Rational for Participatory Action Research as a Transformative Research Design

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is relevant to pressing social issues which are the dichotomous gaps left behind by the perceived social inequalities and the supposed marginalisation of the researched. Using this research design will enable a robust discursive space accommodating matters and the people that live with the matters without fear of unruly power differentials. It also allows all the participants, both the perceived oppressor and the oppressed to discuss and iron out issues on the same level of opportunities. This, according to Tsotetsi (2013) creates an atmosphere for all participants to listen and to be listened to, to express and also decode another person's expressions on the issues that affect them on a daily basis. Since PAR produces and values indigenous knowledge, it becomes imperative to be able to allow the concerned to sit, discuss and proffer solutions to the social problems. This is therefore considered as one of the most effective transformative design for the purpose of taking action to address social issues where the affected people are involved as participants (co-producers of knowledge and action) through interaction, planning, action and review (Jowsey&Desborough, 2016).

This approach is well channelled to operationalise transformative paradigm, which exposes the participation of the people in research processes for the purpose of transformation. I further argue that TP and PAR, in research, create an avenue to unite a homogenous group of people to reflect, analyse and fashion out solutions to social problems for social change. That is, the principles TP are the predominant intention PAR. In order to translate the data gathered with PAR in social research, it is expedient to carefully select an appropriate method of data analysis that will successfully peruse the social issue emanating from the participatory research process. On this perspective, I, therefore, formulate Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) as a method of social data analysis that concurrently dwell on the principles of thematic analysis and Conversational Analysis.

Presentation of Socio-thematic Analysis as a Tool for Analysing Social Issues

This method conjecturally combined two methods of data analysis as complementary tools for qualitative data analysis in social research. The former is the thematic analysis, and the latter is conversational analysis. Data generation in qualitative research is usually attached to deductive, inductive and or logical inferences from various premises of different research instruments. The implication is that all qualitative data requires a rigorous interpretation and explanation based on the type of tools adopted. This is because exhaustive evidence is usually generated during the data generation process and this according to Alhojailan (2012) propels for merging of data interpretation with data analysis, at some point even misplaces it with data generation. This, by implication, shows that there is an overlap of analysis and interpretation to reach a logical, an interpretive and/or a logical conclusion (Cohen, Manion& Morrison, 2011). In order to ensure adequate and robust arrangement, explanation, interpretation with the inculcation of social understanding, the sociology and its socio-linguistic of data that was generated through group discussion bring about the thematic while the involvement of conversational analysis interprets the sociality of the themes.

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis, according to Alhojailan (2012), is suggested to be the first qualitative data method that is concerned with the identification of patterns or themes in qualitative data. It provides skills useful for further kinds of analysis based on the processes involved in its practices (Clarke & Braun, 2013). This is regarded by Braun and Clarke (2006) as a method, rather than being referred to as a methodology. This is an indication that the thematic system of analysing qualitative data is not strictly attached to a definite epistemic perspective. That is, it is flexible enough to accommodate all forms of data analysis for the qualitative research family. From the foregoing, the aims and objectives of thematic analysis remain that: it focuses on identifying themes in the data based on the hierarchy of importance, these themes are thereafter looked into and addressed to construct sense from them. This method of data analysis reflects as a physiognomic summary of data, but it predominantly borders mostly on interpreting with sense-making (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It is on this note I considered the use of Braun and Clarke's thematic model with its six steps framework. The six steps in thematic analysis postulated by Braun and Larke in 2006 are: researcher becomes familiar with the data, generates initial codes, search for themes, review themes, define the themes and write-up (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

Familiarisation, this first stage is where the researcher becomes familiar with the data by reading, reading and rereading the transcribed interview, talks and or discourse. The second stage involves *generating the initial codes*. This is where the researcher begins coding the data such as to generate sentences, phrases, and paragraphs to be labelled under related topics (Braun & Clarke, 2013). The third stage is to *create the initial themes*. This is where the researcher or analyst begins to cluster and categories codes with similar meanings with substantiated relationships. The fourth step is *reviewing the initial themes*, which ensures that the themes

are reviewed against the data without missing any important details. The next step is *naming and defining the themes* according to the extracts and meanings embodied in the themes, and lastly, it is *writing the final report* where the researcher transforms analysis into interpretable pieces of writing and making sense through extracts (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Braun & Clarke, 2013; Vaismoradi, Turunen&Bondas, 2013). The last stage of the thematic analysis of Braun & Clarke (2006), is where the importance of conversational analysis comes in. That is, conversational analysis helps to make sense of the data by understanding its social reality.

Conversational Analysis (CA)

CA originated in between the 1960s-70s by Harvey Sacks, Emanuel Schegloff and Gail Jefferson (Hoey& Kendrick, 2017) from the University of California (Sacks, 1992). The innovation to research community came majorly to uncover the entire domain of sociological inquiry and face-to-face interaction. Sacks and Schegloff who developed this technique were students of Goffman who appreciated interaction as a locus of social organisation that could be investigated in its own right (Garfinkel, 1967). This technique derived its root in any filed that involves conversation, including interaction in educational, legal, and mass media, among others. It also covers social science perspectives with recognition of the nature of human action, interaction in the formation of management and personal identity, social relationships and/or human institutions (Levinson, 2016). This kind of data analysis involves doing things with words to perform social actions such as describing, agreeing, questioning and offering (Nordquist, 2019).

The foregoing confirmed the conclusion of Nordquist (2019) that *conversation analysis* studies the talk produced in human interactions, which is also called *talk-in-interaction and ethnomethodology as a method suitable for working with* audio and video recordings of talk and social interaction (Sidnell, 2010). That is, CA is a method of analysing social interaction in order to understand the sociality involved in the discourse. The aim of this is to discover how participants understand and respond to social issues outside and within themselves in their turns, focusing on how actions are generated. To put it differently, Hutchby and Wooffitt (2008) explained that "the objective of CA is to uncover the often tacit reasoning procedures and socio-linguistic competencies underlying the production and interpretation of talk in organised sequences of interaction". Hence, this method could be regarded as an inductive analysis of qualitative data that study language usage in social interaction, it regards language as a resource for social action and basing analysis on participants' details and behaviours (Wooffitt, 2005; Antaki, 2008). Above all, this approach is needed to complement the thematic analysis to help the researchers to socially interpret the social dependencies and independence and social interactions coming from the differences in personalities of the participants.

Implementation of Socio-thematic Analysis (StA) in Social Research

The system of data analysis will enable the researcher to draw some social and political understanding of the participants, their differences, relationships and sociality. The contextual breaking of data in themes will help to arrange sequentially the necessary steps needed to display a good report, though this is not enough to shed more light into the manner of relationships that exist among people and possible disconnection between them. In order to get into the sociality of the participants, the dual system of analysis became imperative. The implementation procedure is, therefore presented below:

1. **Step One:** The researcher will start by reading and rereading data in order to get familiar with the data after it has been carefully transcribed. In this stage, the researcher will be able to understand the nitty-gritty by jotting down some of the controversial and obviously provoking statements, more especially those with socio-linguistic uncertainty for the purpose of conversational clarity.
2. **Step Two:** Here, the researcher will start with the organisation and arrangement of data in a meaningful and systematic way. This is otherwise called coding. This process will enable him/her to reduce data into meaningful partitioning. This may be done according to research questions and research objectives in order to avoid word misting. In the coding, every relevant segmental statement that addressed the question and objectives will be adequately coded.
3. **Step Three:** In this stage, the researcher will begin by searching for appropriate themes for various related codes. Gathering the codes together, then suggest a relevant topic (theme) to describe better what discussion of sub-topic/theme will focus on. This could be done by the discretion of the researcher since there was no rules, regulations or any generally accepted means to formulate themes because a theme is referred to as a pattern that reflects or captures an interesting and significant data in research (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017:3354). At the end of this step, all coded data would have been organised into broader themes that seemed to speak directly to the research question and objectives.
4. **Step Four:** In this stage, the researcher will develop, modify and review the suggested themes to ensure coherence and cohesion in the thematic segmentation of statements that speaks specifically to

the same themes. Here there will be a lot of personal questions such as; is it relevant to this theme? If yes, how, where and why and for what sense? Are there themes within themes (subthemes)? Are there other themes within data? Does data support the themes? Among others. In doing these, the researcher will read and make sure each data did adequately support its theme.

5. **Step Five:** This is where the themes will be defined, and the essence of each theme will also be identified. Here, the researcher will decode what the themes are saying. The researcher will discover the themes and subthemes, and if yes, what is the connection? All these will give an insight into what they should stand to represent.
6. **Step Six:** This stage is the last step that will be taken to make sense of data. Here the report will be written with noisier conversation which will enable the researcher to rationalise, not only the inference but also read meanings to words in the social order. This, in turn, also lent to fulfil the quest for social understanding. Based on the success in this exploration, this dual data analysis tools, thereby suggested being called *socio-thematic analysis* which is further subjected to be hypothesised by future researchers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the above, it is evidenced that social researches most especially the ones that aim to understand, interpret, and ameliorate social relationships and differences need to engage in a transformative research process. This is expedient because of the democratic nature of the stages and process of solution generation to such a problem. This will not only ensure a genuine solution to the problem using the knowledge and experience of the people who are facing the problem, but also the research will transform the status quo for better. This is what Omodan and Dube (2020) tagged as a methodology that ensures social transformation in universities. In the same vein, the transformative research process is needed to pilot social process of generating solution to the problem of marginalisation, social inequalities, oppression, coloniality, among others. All these are social issues which may not be uncovered without transformational agenda that could emancipate the people and their community (Omodan, 2020). Based on this conclusion, I, therefore, recommend that the use of transformative paradigm, participatory action research as a research design, and Socio-thematic analysis are good to be used when engaging in social researches that are aiming to uncover social issues for the purpose of transformation and emancipation of the people, the population and the community of such research focus.

Reference

- Aasgaard, H. S., Borg, M., & Karlsson, B. (2012). Emancipation or Symbolic Participation: How Can we „do“ Action Research as a Democratic Process. *International Practice Development Journal*, 2(1) 1-7. https://www.fons.org/Resources/Documents/Journal/Vol2No1/IPDJ_0201_08.pdf
- Akinnubi, O. P & Kayode, D. J. (2012). Student personnel services and students' behaviours in University of Ilorin. *Global Journal of Applied Sciences, Management and Social Sciences*. Available online: www.gojemss.com. Retrieved 13/10/2018.
- Akinyeye, T. V. (2019). Administrative Effectiveness in University System: The Trajectory of Students' Involvement in Governance. *Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development*, 1(1), 37-88. <https://jerrcd.org/article/view/19624/13253>
- Akparep, J. Y. (2019). An Examination of the Causes of Students-Management Conflicts in University for Development Studies from 1999 to 2009. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 8, 75-94.
- Alhojailan, M. I. (2012). Thematic analysis: A critical review of its process and evaluation. *West East Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 39-47.
- Aliyu, A. A., Bello, M. U., Kasim, R. & Martin, D. (2014). Positivist and Non-Positivist Paradigm in Social Science Research: Conflicting Paradigms or Perfect Partners? *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 4 (3), 79-95. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/jms.v4n3p79>
- Antaki, C., (2008). Discourse analysis and conversation analysis. IN: Alasuutari, P., Bickman L, and Brannan, J. (eds.). *The SAGE Handbook of Social Research Methods*, London: Sage, pp. 431-446.
- Blythe, J., Gardner, R., Mushin, I. & Stirling, L (2018): Tools of Engagement: Selecting a Next Speaker in Australian Aboriginal Multiparty Conversations, *Research on Language and Social Interaction*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08351813.2018.1449441>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2013). *Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners*. Sage.
- Brown, D., & Tandon, R. (1983). Ideology and political economy in inquiry: Action research and participatory research. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 19(3), 277-294.
- Cameron, J. & Gibson, K. (2005). Participatory action research in a poststructuralist vein. *Geoforum*, 36, 315-331.

- Chalmers, A. (1982). *What is this thing called science?* Queensland, Australia: University of Queensland.
- Chilisa, B. & Kawulich, B. (2012). Selecting a research approach: Paradigm, methodology and methods. 1-12. https://www.academia.edu/15804348/Selecting_a_research_approach_Paradigm_methodology_and_methods
- Chilisa, B. (2011). *Indigenous Research Methodologies*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Clarke, V. & Braun, V. (2013). Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The Psychologist*, 26(2), 120-123.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011). *Research Methods in Education*. 7th ed. Routledge.
- Crotty, M. (1998). *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: Sage.
- Dammak, A. (2019). Research Paradigms: Methodologies and Compatible Methods. <http://stclements.edu/Articles/Research-Paradigms-Full-Article.pdf>. 09/06/2020.
- Dean, B. A. (2018). The interpretivist and the learner. *International Journal of Doctoral Studies*, 13, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.28945/3936>
- Denscombe, M. (2007). *The good research guide for small-scale social research projects*. (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Dilshad, R. M. & Latif, M. I. (2013). Focus Group Interview as a Tool for Qualitative Research: An Analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 33(1), 191-198.
- Dube, B. & Hlalele, D. (2018). Engaging critical emancipatory research as an alternative to mitigate school violence in South Africa. *Educational Research for Social Change*, 7(2), 74-86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/2221-4070/2018/v7i2a5>.
- Dube, B. (2016). *A socio-religious hybridity strategy to respond to the problems of religious studies in Zimbabwe*. Ph.D Thesis, Faculty of Education, University of the Free State.
- Eric, C. A. & Urho, P. (2015). Effects of Strike Actions on Educational Management Planning of Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria-Africa. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3 (11), 28-36.
- Eruera, M. (2010). Ma TeWhānauTeHuarahiMotuhake: Whānau Participatory Action Research groups. *MAI Review*, 3, 1-9.
- Escalada M. & Heong K. L. (2014). *Focus Group Discussion*. [Online] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242589494_Focus_Group_Discussion_1 retrieved 14/06/2020.
- Finnis, J. (1980). *Natural Law and Natural Rights*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Fixico, D.L. (1998). Ethics and responsibilities in writing American Indian history. In D.A. Mihesuah (Ed.). *Natives and academics: Researching and writing about American Indians*, (pp. 84-99). Lincoln, Nebraska: University of Nebraska Press.
- Francis, D. (2012). Border crossing: Conversations about race, identity, and agency in South Africa. *Culture, Education, and community: Expressions of the postcolonial imaginations*. Edited by Lavia, J. & Mahlomaholo, S. New York: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Garfinkel, H. (1967). *Studies in ethnomethodology*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Grix, J. (2004). *The foundation of research*. London, Palgrave: Macmillan.
- Guba, E., & Lincoln, Y. (1994). Competing paradigm in qualitative research. In Denzin, N. & Lincoln, Y. (Eds.). *Handbook of qualitative research* (pp.99-136). Sage Publications.
- Hoey, E. M. & Kendrick, K. H. (2017). Conversation Analysis. In A. M. B. de Groot & P. Hagoort (eds.), *Research Methods in Psycholinguistics: A Practical Guide*. Wiley Blackwell.
- Hutchby, I. & Wooffitt, B. (2008). *Conversation Analysis*. (2nded.) Cambridge: Polity.
- Igwenagu, C. (2016). Fundamentals of research methodology and data collection. <file:///C:/Users/bolab/Downloads/FundamentalsofResearchMethodologyandDataCollection.pdf>/09/06/2020.
- Jowsey T. & Desborough, J. 2016. Qualitative methodology made easy. Centre for Medical and Health Sciences Education, University of Auckland. <https://www.fmhs.auckland.ac.nz/en/som/cmhse/our-resources.html>
- Kaushik, V. & Walsh, C. A. (2019). Pragmatism as a Research Paradigm and Its Implications for Social Work Research. *Social Sciences*, 8(9), 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8090255>**
- Kemmis, S. & McTaggart, R. (2005). Participatory action research: communicative action and the public sphere. In: Denzin, Norman K., and Lincoln, Yvonna S., (eds.) *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*. California, USA: Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks.
- Kemmis, S. & McTaggart, R. (2007). Communicative action and public sphere .In N.K. Denzil & Y.S. Lincoln (Eds). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research*. 559-603. Thousand Oaks. CA.Sage.
- Khan, C. & Chovanec, D. M. (2010). Is Participatory Action Research Relevant in the Canadian Workplace?..*Journal of Contemporary Issues in Education*, 5(1),34-44.

- Kivunja, C. &Kuyini, A. B. (2017). Understanding and Applying Research Paradigms in Educational Contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), 26-41. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p26>**
- Kivunja, C. &Kuyini, A. B. (2017). Understanding and Applying Research Paradigms in Educational Contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), 26-41.
- Kothari C.R., (2004). *Research Methodology* (2nd edition) New –Delhi India: New Age International Publishers.
- Krueger, R. A. (1994). *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc.
- Krueger, R. A., & Casey, M. A. (2000). *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*, 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. (1st Edn). Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Lather, P. (1986). Research as praxis. *Harvard Educational Review*, 56(3), 257-277. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.56.3.bj2h231877069482>
- Levinson, S. C. (2016). Turn-taking in human communication: Origins and implications for language processing. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 20, 6-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.10.010>
- MacDonald, C. 2012. Understanding Participatory Action Research: A Qualitative Research Methodology Option. *Canadian Journal of Action Research*, 13(2):34-50.
- Mack, L. (2010). The Philosophical Underpinnings of Educational Research. https://en.apu.ac.jp/rcaps/uploads/fckeditor/publications/polyglossia/Polyglossia_V19_Lindsay.pdf/10/06/2020.
- Mackenzie, N. &Knipe, S. (2006). Research dilemmas: paradigms, methods and methodology. *Issues In Educational Research*, 16, 1-15.
- Mafuwane, B. M. (2011). The contribution of instructional leadership to learner performance. Phd Thesis, University of Pretoria, South Africa.
- Maguire, M. & Delahunt, B. (2017). Doing a Thematic Analysis: A Practical, Step-by-Step Guide for Learning and Teaching Scholars. *All Ireland Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 8(3), 3351-3354. <http://ojs.aishe.org/index.php/aishe-j/article/view/335>
- Mahlomaholo, M.G. &Netshandama, V.O. (2010). Sustainable Empowering Learning Environments: Conversations with Gramsci's Organic Intellectual. Presented at the Intellectual, Knowledge and Power: Ideas for Inter-Disciplinary Conference in Prague, Czech Republic and published in Basov, N. Simet, G F., van Anandel J., Mahlomaholo, MG and Netshandama, V. (eds) *The Intellectual. A Phenomenon in Multidimensional Perspectives*. Interdisciplinary Press, Oxford and [http://www.inter-disciplinary.net /](http://www.inter-disciplinary.net/), ISBN: 978-1-84888-027-6.
- Mertens, D. M. & Wilson, A. T. (2012). *Program Evaluation Theory and Practice*. New York: Guilford.
- Mertens, D. M. (2005). *Research and evaluation education and psychology: integrating diversity with quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods*. London: SAGE publishers.
- Mertens, D. M. (2010). Philosophy in mixed methods teaching: The transformative paradigm as illustration. *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches*, 4, 9–18.
- Mertens, D. M. 2009. *Transformative research and evaluation*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Mertens, D.M. (2007). Transformative paradigm, mixed methods and social justice. *Journal of mixed methods research* 1(3):212-225.
- Mertens, D.M. 2017. Advances in Mixed Methods Design. *Webinar Mixed Methods International Research Association*, 1-19. <https://www.ualberta.ca/international-institute-for-qualitative-methodology/media-library/international-institute-of-qualitative-methods/webinars/mixed-methods/2017/dmertensadvances-in-mm-designfinal.pdf>
- Mihesuah, D. A. (2005). *So you want to write about American Indians? A guide for writers, students, and scholars*. Lincoln, Nebraska: University of Nebraska Press.
- Morales, M. P. E. (2016). Participatory Action Research (PAR) cum Action Research (AR) in teacher professional development: A literature review. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 2(1), 156-165.
- Nordquist, R. (2019). Conversation Analysis (CA): Glossary of Grammatical and Rhetorical Terms. <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-conversation-analysis-ca-1689923>. 16/06/2020.**
- Nyumba, T. O., Wilson, K., Derrick, C. J. & Mukherjee, N. (2017). The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation. *Method in Ecology and Evaluation*, 9, 20–32.
- Omodan, B. I. &Dube B. (2020). Towards De-colonial Agitations in University Classrooms: The Quest for Afrocentric Pedagogy. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(4), 14-28. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.4.2>

- Omodan, B. I. (2020). The Vindication of Decoloniality and the Reality of COVID-19 as an Emergency of Unknown in Rural Universities. *International Journal of Sociology of Education*, 20, 1-26. <http://doi.org/10.17583/rise.2020.5495>
- Patton, M.Q. 2002. *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Qhosola, M. R. (2016). Creating sustainable learning environments for a grade 10 accounting classroom: A critical accounting approach. Ph.D. Thesis, university of the Free State, South Africa.
- Rabiee, F. (2004). Focus-group interview and data analysis. *Proceedings of Nutrition Society*, 63, 655–660.
- Reason, P. and Bradbury, H. (2008). The SAGE Handbook of Action Research. *Introduction*. In P. Reason, & H. Bradbury (Eds.). 1-11. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781848607934>
- Rehman, A. A. & Alharthi, K. (2010). An Introduction to Research Paradigms. *International Journal of Educational Investigations*, 3(8), 51-59.
- Romm, N. R. A. (2015). Reviewing the Transformative Paradigm: A Critical Systemic and Relational (Indigenous) Lens. *System Practice Action Research*, 28, 411–427.
- Sacks, H. (1992). *Lectures on conversation*, Vols. 1 & 2, edited by G. Jefferson. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Sakyi, K. A. 2017. Research Method and Methodology. https://www.academia.edu/33599596/THREE_TYPES_OF_RESEARCH_AND_RESEARCH_PARADIGMS/09/06/2020.
- Schegloff, E. A. (1996). Confirming allusions: Toward an empirical account of action. *American Journal of Sociology*, 102, 161–216. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bda6/acc07551a1bca293dc8dfbd1fbff055fcd96.pdf>
- Scotland, J. (2012). Exploring the philosophical underpinnings of research: Relating ontology and epistemology to the methodology and methods of the scientific, interpretive, and critical research paradigms. *English Language Teaching*, 5(9), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v5n9p9>
- Seale, C. (2000). *The Quality of Qualitative Research*. London: Sage.
- Seymour-Rolls, K., & Hughes, I. (2000). *Participatory Action Research: Getting the Job Done*, Action Research E-Reports, 004, September.
- Shah, R. S. & Al-Bargi, A. 2013. Research Paradigms: Researchers' Worldviews, Theoretical Frameworks and Study Designs. *Arab World English Journal*, 4(4), 252 -264.
- Sidnell, J. (2010). *Conversation analysis: An Introduction*. Malden: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Swartz, S. & Nyamnjoh, A. (2018). Research as freedom: Using a continuum of interactive, participatory and emancipatory methods for addressing youth marginality, HTS Theologiese Studies/Theological Studies 74(3), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v74i3.5063>
- Tshelane, M. D. (2013). Participatory action research and the construction of academic identity among postgraduate research students. *The Journal for Transdisciplinary Research in Southern Africa*, 9(3), 401-429.
- Tsotetsi, C. T. (2013). The implementation of professional teacher development policies: A continuing education perspective. Ph.D. thesis, University of the Free State, South Africa.
- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H. & Bondas, T. (2013). Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study. *Nursing and Health Sciences*, 15, 398–405. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nhs.12048>
- Waismann, F. (2011). *Causality and logical positivism*. In *Humanities, Social Science and Law*. Resource Type: Springer eBooks.
- Wisker, G. (2001). *The postgraduate research handbook*. U.K.: Palgrave.
- Wood, L. & McAteer, M. (2017). Levelling the Playing Fields in PAR: The Intricacies of Power, Privilege, and Participation in a University–Community–School Partnership. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 67(4) 251–265.
- Wooffitt, R. (2005). *Conversation Analysis and Discourse Analysis*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Zuber-Skerritt, O. (2015). Conceptual framework. In O. Zuber-Skerritt, M. Fletcher, & J. Kearney (Eds.), *Professional learning in higher education and communities: Towards anew vision of action research* (1-37). London, England: Palgrave MacMillan.

Author Information

Bunmi Isaiah Omodan, PhD.

Lecturer, School of Education Studies, University of the Free State, Qwqwa Campus Private Bag X13, Phuthaditjhaba 9866, Republic of South Africa
